

ENACT

Efficient Edge-to-Cloud Workload Management

Title	ENACT Application Programming Model and SDK for Hyper-Distributed Applications
Document Owners	SIE
Contributors	SIE, ICE, DNET, DS4, UOWM
Dissemination	Public (PU)
Date	30/06/2025
Version	V1.0

Version History

Nr.	Date	Author (Organization)	Description
0.1	26/02/2025	Gabriel Danciu (SIE)	Deliverable structure
0.2	03/03/2025	Vlad Mocanu (SIE)	Replaced placeholders, added section descriptions
0.3	15/03/2025	Mihnea Lopataru (SIE)	Created draft content for SDK
0.4	30/03/2025	Vlad Mocanu (SIE)	Created draft content for APM
0.5	05/05/2025	Gabriel Danciu (SIE)	Update the draft version for SDK and APM
0.6	28/05/2025	Mihnea Lopataru(SIE)	Added content to the use cases
0.7	04/06/2025	Vlad Mocanu (SIE)	Added references, corrected errors
0.8	16/06/2025	Gabriel Danciu, Vlad Mocanu (SIE)	Internal review version
0.9	26/06/2025	ALL Partners	Updates and final improvements
1.0	30/06/2025	Vlad Mocanu (SIE)	Submitted version

Disclaimer

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Acknowledgement

The ENACT project is funded by the Horizon Europe Program of the European Commission under **Grant Agreement 101135423**.

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List of Abbreviations

AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
APM	Application Programming Model
CCC	Cognitive Computing Continuum
CLI	Command Line Interface
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
DNS	Domain Name System

DoS	Denial of Service
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DGM	Data Governance Module
DTU	Digital Twin Utilizer
E2C	Edge-to-Cloud
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GPS	Global Positioning System
HLS	HTTP Live Streaming
HTTP/HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol / Secure
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
IoT	Internet of Things
JAR	Java ARchive
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JWT	JSON Web Token
KMS	Key Management Service
MARL	Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning
MinIO	High-performance object storage system
mTLS	Mutual Transport Layer Security
OSGi	Open Services Gateway initiative
PG	PostgreSQL
PGP	Pretty Good Privacy
PU	Public
QA	Quality Assurance
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAM	Random Access Memory
REST	Representational State Transfer
RSA	Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (cryptographic algorithm)
SDK	Software Development Kit
SH	State Handler
SSH	Secure Shell
SRM	Security Risk Modeller
TDCME	Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UI	User Interface
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language (recursive acronym)
ZTP	Zero Touch Provisioning

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the activities, objectives, and key technical advancements achieved within the ENACT Horizon project [1], focusing on the development of the Application Programming Model (APM) and the Software Development Kit (SDK). These tools have been designed to facilitate secure, modular, and scalable application development across a hyper-distributed edge-to-cloud computing continuum.

The APM provides a collection of Java libraries that enable controlled and exclusive access to the ENACT Cognitive Computing Continuum (CCC), ensuring that applications can programmatically interact with platform services in a secure manner. A major evolution in the APM's architecture was the shift from being an active component within the CCC to becoming a set of downloadable libraries distributed via Maven Central [2]. This transformation enhances usability, compliance with industry standards, and integration with modern development environments.

The SDK complements the APM by offering both a library version for experienced developers and an Eclipse plugin version aimed at users with limited programming expertise. It abstracts complex platform interactions and automates code generation, configuration, and deployment workflows. The SDK significantly lowers the barrier to entry for building ENACT-compliant applications.

The deliverable captures the iterative development process, from requirements analysis to implementation and deployment. It also showcases applied scenarios across different industrial use cases (MOG[3], Osoigo [4], Fujitsu[5]), which validate the versatility and impact of the APM and SDK tools in real-world deployments. These efforts contribute to the ENACT mission of enabling secure, interoperable, and developer-friendly solutions for hyper-distributed applications.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverables

The purpose of this deliverable is to document the design, implementation, and deployment of the ENACT Application Programming Model (APM) and the Software Development Kit (SDK). These tools collectively aim to streamline the development and orchestration of hyper-distributed applications operating within the ENACT ecosystem.

The APM is a security-first programming framework that enables structured and exclusive access to CCC services via downloadable Java libraries. The SDK, on the other hand, provides higher-level abstractions and graphical interfaces that assist users in creating and managing ENACT-compliant software.

2.2 Relation to other WPs and tasks

This deliverable is closely integrated with the objectives of several Work Packages (WPs) within the ENACT project, reflecting its foundational role in enabling hyper-distributed applications through secure and scalable software tooling.

Primarily, it aligns with the WP6 tasks:

T6.1 Design and Specification of ENACT Application Programming Model by developing the specifications for the APM.

T6.2 Application-Level Adaptation, Elasticity, Load Balancing and Energy Efficiency Characterization: by enforcing secure, exclusive access to Core Cloud Components through the APM and supporting controlled execution of application logic.

T6.3 Quality, Security and Privacy Policy Models for Hyper Distributed Applications by aligning with security enforcement mechanisms such as telemetry monitoring, user authorization, and access control policies integrated within the APM and SDK.

T6.4 Software Development Kit (SDK): as the core focus of this deliverable, documenting its design, implementation, and integration capabilities.

In addition, the APM and SDK deliverables support and are influenced by:

- WP5 – Resource and Service Orchestration, especially: T5.2 Graph Neural Networks for Scheduling and Dynamic Optimization of Hyper-Distributed Applications and T5.4 Virtual Environment for Training, Retraining and Recalibration of AI Models, by providing APIs and structural components that facilitate dynamic deployment of models, and policy compliance across the compute continuum.
- WP4 – ENACT Platform components, notably through interactions with components like the Telemetry and Data Collection & Monitoring Engine (TDCME), the Zero Touch Provisioning (ZTP), and Security Risk Modeler (SRM), as defined in T4.1–T4.3. These dependencies ensure consistent and secure integration of runtime intelligence and service-level adaptations.
- WP2 – Specification and Architecture, since the design of the APM and SDK has been aligned with the architecture defined in D2.1-D2.6, particularly in terms of component roles, interfaces, and compliance with the Cognitive Compute Continuum vision.

This synergy ensures that the tools described in this deliverable not only serve their direct objectives but also act as enablers for system-wide interoperability, policy enforcement, and seamless deployment across all ENACT pilot scenarios.

2.3 Structure of the deliverables

The structure of the document is organized as follows:

Section 2: Introduction which gives an overview of this deliverable.

Section 3: Requirement Analysis outlines the core technical and operational requirements that shaped the development of the APM and SDK.

Section 4: Application Programming Model (APM) details the conceptual framework, architectural evolution, deployment mechanisms, and integration paths for the APM libraries.

Section 5: Software Development Kit (SDK) explains the dual-version SDK implementation (library and Eclipse plugin), including templates, workflows, and user experiences.

Section 6: Applied Scenarios demonstrate real-world use cases from industrial partners, showcasing the tools' applicability and performance.

Section 7: Conclusions chapter summarizes key outcomes and provides a roadmap for future developments.

3. Requirement analysis

Requirement analysis regarding the APM

The Application Programming Model (APM) serves as the foundational framework for secure and structured interactions with the ENACT platform. By offering a controlled yet user-friendly environment through Java libraries, it enables end users to efficiently integrate and utilize CCC components. Since the design phase, the APM has been defined by a set of requirements that dictate its behavior and functionality. It must be developed using open-source libraries and resources (C12.2), offer support for dynamic application development (C12.3) and applications developed using the APM jars directly (by manually adding the APM dependencies) or indirectly (via the SDK) must be configurable when it comes to priorities, policies and constraints (C12.4). Initial requirements also include CRUD-like operation with compatible components (C12.5) and application deployment management and monitoring (C12.7).

Since the initial planning phases, these requirements have been updated in order to reflect the current direction of the APM, especially after the major paradigm shift from functional self-standing entity, deployed inside Enact CCC to collection of publicly available JARs deployed on a public repository. Thus, the updated version of open requirements from C12.1 to C12.7 reflects the usage of the APM, from the end user's point of view, as a series of JARs, downloaded and deployed on the end user's development station.

In order to support the lifecycle of the APM as a core component of application flows, two new requirements have been added, C12.8 and C12.9. The necessity of exclusive access has been captured within requirement C12.8. All existing and future tasks under this requirement will handle the development of a system that ensures that ENACT CCC is accessible to the end user only through the APM. Requirement C12.9 refers to having the APM JARs deployed on a public repository. In future, this requirement will also house the APM offered as a series of publicly available Python modules.

APM requirements have been described in detail within the WP2 deliverables and can be found on the official ENACT APM Gitlab page [6].

Requirement analysis regarding the SDK

The Software Development Kit (SDK) for the Enact platform has been designed to support a wide range of developer needs, streamline component integration, and ensure secure, standardized access to Enact services. This dual-purpose toolkit is provided in two complementary forms: a Maven-based library version tailored for experienced developers, and an Eclipse [7] plug-in[8] version aimed at simplifying access through a graphical interface and automated code generation. This flexibility enables both power users and less technical stakeholders to effectively interact with the Enact platform.

The requirement analysis has led to the identification of a set of core functionalities the SDK must support. These include the ability to generate Java code dynamically based on user-selected services (C16.5), deploying a standardized template library for consistent component integration (C16.3), and providing multiple options for importing services, whether in bulk or selectively (C16.7). Additionally, the SDK must support interaction with the Application Programming Model (APM) (C16.1, C16.4), integrate with pilot workflows (C16.12), and allow for deployment through both Maven and Eclipse

Marketplace [8] channels (C16.2, C16.11, C16.14). To ensure security and maintain platform integrity, the SDK is also expected to establish and enforce strict access controls (C16.13). These requirements have been progressively addressed, with most already implemented or in active development, reflecting a robust and modular approach to enabling scalable, secure, and user-friendly SDK adoption across the ENACT ecosystem.

SDK requirements have been described in detail within the WP2 deliverables and can be found on the official ENACT APM Gitlab page [9].

4. Application Programming Model (APM)

The Application Programming Model (APM) exposes the backbone for secure and structured interactions with the ENACT platform. It provides an accessible yet controlled environment through Java libraries, ensuring end users can effectively integrate and leverage CCC components.

4.1 Design approach

This subsection discusses the foundational design principles of the APM, emphasizing the secure, exclusive, and controlled access to the ENACT platform's CCC components. It highlights considerations in security, access control, and user interaction paradigms.

Figure 1: ENACT Architecture with APM highlighted

As seen in Figure 1, the Application Programming Model is an essential component of the ENACT project although it doesn't have an active presence within the CCC. It comprises of a series of Java libraries that are being downloaded from Maven Central by the end users outside the CCC and used, directly or through SDK, to access ENACT's internal environment. The set of libraries and thus the behavior of the APM is unique to each end user, as the APM's functionality is split into separate libraries, each encapsulating one of the CCC components, or specific interactions between the components.

The direct goal of the APM is to facilitate complete, secured and exclusive access to CCC components (see Figure 2), even if ease of access and user friendliness receive a lower priority. Functionality customization and end user experience are not goals within the APM's reach and are thus delegated to the SDK.

Figure 2: User interaction with the CCC using the APM

Complete access is achieved by granting access to all components' endpoints, wrapping all possible features of each individual component endpoint and providing access to them. As expected, this is done in correlation with the components' specifications and design, and everything is done in a need-to-know fashion.

Secured access to the CCC is achieved by implementing industry standard security measures for communicating with the components and transferring information, like HTTPS [10]/TLS [12] for transport encryption (thus protecting against eavesdropping and man-in-the-middle attacks [12]), Content-Type validation and input sanitization (ensuring the endpoints only accept and provide expected file types and prevent injection attacks), rate limiting and throttling (preventing abuse/Denial of Service attacks [13] by rate-limiting uploads/downloads, especially for large files like video content).

Additionally, secured access can be further strengthened by implementing multiple layers of protection for local temporary storage on the end-user's environment. This includes enforcing periodic cleanup of temporary files, applying AES-256 encryption [14] for sensitive content, and managing cryptographic keys using established solutions like AWS Key Management Service (KMS) [15] or Vault [16]. Integrity verification mechanisms, such as checksum validation and digital signature checks, should also be applied during file transfers to detect tampering or data corruption.

However, securing the client-side environment alone is not sufficient for complete threat mitigation. To provide centralized oversight and enhance threat detection, there may be a need for a lightweight APM monitoring counterpart deployed within the CCC layer of the ENACT platform.

This CCC-hosted module would not expose any direct user-facing API but would operate passively by observing and validating incoming requests originating from APM-based clients. Its primary responsibilities would include:

- Detecting anomalous behavior patterns, such as unusually high-frequency API calls, which could indicate automated abuse, misconfigurations, or compromised user environments.
- Identifying geographic or network-origin anomalies, such as unexpected access attempts from non-whitelisted IP ranges or geolocations inconsistent with the user's historical behavior.
- Monitoring for invalid request signatures, malformed payloads, or repeated failed authentication attempts, which could signal malicious activities like credential stuffing or replay attacks.
- Enforcing rate limits and request throttling policies centrally, to prevent any one user from overloading individual CCC services.
- Forwarding security alerts to the ENACT monitoring and SIEM infrastructure, ensuring that platform operators are notified of any suspected breaches or abnormal usage.

By complementing the client-side APM JARs with this CCC-side validation and monitoring layer, ENACT implements a defense-in-depth approach that addresses both external threats and insider misuse, while maintaining the exclusivity and controlled access principles defined for APM interactions.

Exclusive access is needed to ensure that the ENACT components can only be used through the APM jars. Security has the highest priority, however user access control and monitoring as well as a foundation for user licenses and subscriptions are also relevant for the APM and the ENACT project, especially when considering the roadmap towards a hypothetical production pilot phase. The exclusive access goal is achieved by implementing industry standard authentication and authorization mechanisms like OAuth 2.0 [17], JSON Web Tokens [18] or Mutual TLS (mTLS) [19] within the APM jars. Additionally, the user can provide a locally stored private key that is matched with a public key stored within the CCC, in order to grant access to the ENACT components.

Figure 3: Example of user interacting with multiple CCC components

Figure 3 portrays a common interaction between the end user and multiple components from within the CCC. The components are not publicly accessible by other means than through the APM jars. The APM, although technically an ENACT component, has no functional presence within the CCC, but instead is downloaded, manually or through the SDK, in the end user's environment. From there it telegraphs all user's requests to the CCC, if the user is authorized to use the desired components.

4.2 Implementation of the APM

This subsection explores the implementation journey of the APM, detailing the significant paradigm shift from internal CCC components to external Java libraries, available through Maven Central [2].

Figure 4: First version of APM deployment before paradigm shift

As seen in Figure 4, the initial version of the APM was designed as a collection of active functional entities within the CCC, with a reverse proxy (NGINX) [20] acting as a gateway for end users to access the ENACT platform services. Each APM module was developed as a Java backend-only web application using Spring Boot [21], containerized via Docker [22], and exposed its own API to wrap and manage the corresponding CCC component's functionality.

The "MAAS Server" referenced in Figure 4 refers to Canonical's Metal-as-a-Service (MAAS) platform, an open-source tool designed for the automated provisioning and management of bare-metal servers within private networks.

Canonical MAAS was selected due to several factors:

- Its maturity and stability for managing on-premises server infrastructure, making it suitable for ENACT's private, cloud-like deployment environments.
- Native support for PXE booting, resource pooling, and dynamic provisioning, all of which aligned well with the project's Zero Touch Provisioning (ZTP) objectives.
- Existing partner familiarity and integration experience with MAAS in other EU-funded projects and industrial settings.

While other bare-metal provisioning tools (such as Foreman or Cobbler) were technically feasible alternatives, MAAS offered the most straightforward integration path given ENACT's Kubernetes-based architecture and the need for API-driven control over physical nodes. This made it a pragmatic and low-risk choice for the initial APM deployment scenarios.

Figure 5: Final version of APM deployment before paradigm shift

Figure 5 presents the final iteration of the APM deployment before the paradigm shift, building on the earlier design shown in Figure 4. This version consolidated all APM modules into a lightweight Kubernetes (K3s [24]) cluster, improving scalability and internal communication.

Several modules—such as the Incubator, Telemetry Simulator, and ZTP Simulator—are marked with dotted lines, indicating that they were temporary simulators or placeholders created to support SDK development during periods when the real components were unavailable. Although the actual ZTP component was operational, its simulator remained for fallback and testing purposes.

This architecture addressed short-term scalability and management goals but remained misaligned with the original project vision of providing the APM as external, downloadable libraries (JARs). This gap led directly to the upcoming architectural shift described in the following section.

Within several iterations of the same paradigm, not yet shifted, the APM was deployed in a similar fashion to the Docker-based container approach mentioned for Figure 4, but this time orchestrated on a lightweight Kubernetes (K3s [24]) cluster with two replicas for redundancy. The ZTP component itself was also deployed on a separate K3s cluster within the Components Layer.

This Kubernetes-based deployment maintained the same fundamental architecture, with APM modules acting as active services within the private network, but improved scalability and inter-component communication. However, it still remained within the pre-paradigm shift model, where the APM was a cluster of internal services rather than external libraries.

This approach allowed easier inter-component operability, future expansion, stable and performant operation through redundancy and scalability provided by the Kubernetes clusters and an overall simplified position of the APM within the ENACT landscape. It offered the user the initially planned scalability, stability and performance features. This direction deviates from the original specifications and requirements, as they were stated in the Grant Agreement [25], on the topic of the APM being a

series of libraries (e.g. JARs) that the user chooses to select and download from a public central repository (e.g. Maven Central [2]).

Figure 6: APM Deployment after paradigm shift

The topic of the APM's form and identity has been discussed exhaustively with all partners and a unanimous decision has been made to shift the APM from being a group of components inside the CCC, with public facing APIs, to being a series of JARs that the user can download from Maven Central, and use either directly, or through the SDK (as portrayed in Figure 6). The shift to a completely external position meant that all components must provide their corresponding APM JARs with an endpoint through which the JARs can exchange information.

Massive refactoring has been performed on the APM code itself as well as the SDK, while former components were removed or repurposed into simulators for debugging, testing or replacing potential downtimes. All partners responsible for other APM components are implementing their component's corresponding endpoints, external/public jar and, if possible, a simulator that can be deployed to support the development of the SDK.

In its current iteration the APM is only offered as Java libraries, for Maven managed projects, downloadable from the Enact Horizon Maven Central namespace [27].

The future of the APM remains closely tied to its current format as a collection of JARs available on Maven Central, with a continued focus on secure and exclusive access to CCC. While the current mechanism preventing users from bypassing the APM remains relatively basic, ongoing efforts—with support from responsible partners—aim to enhance this enforcement and expand the library of available APM JARs, strengthening integration with the SDK and enriching end-user capabilities.

Looking ahead, there are plans to extend APM availability to Python 3, driven both by specific pilot partner requests—where Python plays a key role in data processing and AI orchestration pipelines—and by the language's widespread adoption in cloud services and scientific computing domains. This evolution aligns with the ENACT platform's broader goal of supporting multiple developer profiles

and technology stacks, ensuring accessibility for a wider range of application scenarios and user expertise levels.

4.3 Setup

The Application Programming Model JARs require the end user to have some form of a secure connection with the ENACT environment. In the future this will require the user to be authorized to use the ENACT components (e.g. API key, secret token, license, subscription), and some local configurations be performed (with the help of the SDK, if the user decides to go this way). Currently, in order to connect to Siemens' [29] testbed, this involves installing the Cloudflare's [30] Cloudflared CLI tool [31], creating a valid set of SSH [32] public/private keys and creating an SSH tunnel [33]. Alternatively, all components can be deployed locally and the APM JARs instructed to connect to local endpoints.

4.4 Deployment

One of the specifications of the APM is that the user has the ability to select which APM modules they would like to use for their application. Considering that the APM is a series of JARs that can be downloaded from the Maven Central public repository (Figure 7 shows the APM ZTP library page), the specification is respected due to the way Maven manages dependencies within projects configured correctly. That being said, in order to offer a user-friendly experience, the user will not be tasked to maintain configurations files (like Maven specific pom.xml) but instead the SDK will take care of ensuring the module selection is taken into account.

Figure 7: APM ZTP jar on Maven Central

4.4.1 Deployment via Jar files

```
<dependency>
  <groupId>eu.enact-horizon</groupId>
  <artifactId>apm-ztp</artifactId>
  <version>0.1</version>
</dependency>
```

Figure 8: Dependency snippet for APM ZTP jar

Users that prefer using the APM JARs directly and bypassing the SDK will not benefit from the support the SDK provides but instead will have to manually update the pom.xml file so that their project has access to the ENACT environment. Due to the way Maven [34] managed projects are structured; the only requirement is to add the desired dependencies snippets (e.g. the code displayed in Figure 8) to the pom.xml file.

Once the dependency has been added, the APM specific Java code can be used to interact with the desired ENACT component (please refer to the individual component JAR documentation for detailed implementation guide and code snippets). Figure 9 showcases some code samples how one interacts with the ZTP component directly using the APM JARs.

```
import com.siemens.enact.apm.ztp_libs.ZTPComponent;

public class RunMe {

    private static ZTPComponent ztpService = new ZTPComponent();

    public static void main(String[] args) throws IOException, InterruptedException{

        //query all available machines
        List<ZTPComponent.MachineInformation> allMachines = ztpService.retrieveAllMachines();

        //select random machine
        ZTPComponent.MachineInformation randomMachine = allMachines.get(new Random().nextInt(allMachines.size()));
        String randomMachineId = randomMachine.machineId;
        System.out.println("Random machine id: "+randomMachineId);

        System.out.println("Power state: "+randomMachine.powerState);

        //perform "powerOn" action on randomMachine
        ztpService.performAction("powerOn", randomMachineId);

        //update randomMachine information
        randomMachine = ztpService.retrieveMachine(randomMachineId);
        System.out.println("Power state: "+randomMachine.powerState);

        return;
    }
}
```

Figure 9: Sample code of using the APM ZTP jar

4.4.2 Integration via Maven Central

All JARs that are meant to be available to public access, whether these include the APM JARs or other ones (e.g. code templates or conventions introduced by the SDK) are deployed on a Maven Central public repository, under the eu.enact-horizon namespace [27]. In order to be able to publish code to a Maven Central repository, a complex process must be completed.

The process starts with creating a Sonatype account (Figure 10 displays the Sonatype sign up screen [35]). Although social logins are supported, it is recommended to create an account using the traditional method (username and password) to ensure compatibility with Sonatype’s Maven Central deployment tools, which often require API generation and PGP signing processes linked to standard account credentials. An email address is required for both methods.

Figure 10: Sonatype sign up screen

Once the account has been created, a namespace is required that will host multiple deployments. The ENACT public JARs are hosted under the **eu.enact-horizon** namespace. A newly created namespace is not public (as seen in Figure 11) as a verification step is required. Namespace verification can be done through DNS validation, by adding a DNS TXT record (within the DNS registrar or web hosting provider) with a value set to the Verification Key (provided by Sonatype) or by linking a Gitlab code repository. The downside using the second option is that the namespace will follow the naming rule *“io.gitlab.xxx”*. The ENACT public repository namespace was verified through the DNS approach.

Figure 11: Unverified namespace

eu.enact-horizon

Verified

Figure 12: Verified namespace

Once the namespace has been created and verified (Figure 12 showcases the “Verified” tag indicating that a namespace is verified), the next steps focus on creating deployments within the newly created namespace. Although code can be deployed by using the Maven CLI, the following set of requirements must be fulfilled:

1. Code must be packaged as JAR.
2. JAR files must be accompanied by a javadoc and sources.
3. All files sent to Sonatype must be signed using a valid PGP [36] signature.
4. Publishing must be done using valid Sonatype credentials.

The first two requirements can be fulfilled by using a pom.xml file in which the code project is configured to be built as JAR (1) and the correct plugins are added (*maven-compiler-plugin*, *maven-gpg-plugin*, *central-publishing-maven-plugin*, *maven-jar-plugin*, *maven-source-plugin*, *maven-javadoc-plugin*). The file must also contain mandatory fields required by Sonatype to allow code to be published on Maven Central. A detailed deployment guide has been created [28].

In order to be able to sign all published materials, a PGP key must be created by using an appropriate tool like GnuPG/gpg. The key must be of type RSA with a size of 4096 bits, use the info@enact-horizon.eu email and a have valid passphrase. Once the key has been created it must be published on the Hockeypuck OpenPGP Ubuntu KeyServer [26]. With the PGP key created and published, Maven must be configured to use the correct API credentials (the page displayed in Figure 13 contains the options that allow for user access token management) and the correct PGP key, to enable code deployment. Code deployed successfully can then be published, as seen in Figure 14.

Figure 13: Authentication token management screen

Figure 14: Validated and published deployment

4.5 Interactions between APM and SDK

Application Programming Models JARs can be used directly, by adding the Maven dependency snippet to the project's Maven configuration file `pom.xml`. In this case, the end user is recommended to follow the documentation and usage instructions/examples from each individual ENACT component APM jar in order to benefit from the component's functionality. For users that are not comfortable with using the JARs directly and/or do not have the domain knowledge to manually configure each component functionality function, it is recommended to use the Software Development Kit, the official ENACT Eclipse plugin.

Without going into details, the SDK offers assistance with developing applications that use the APM to interact with the CCC components. From code generation to deployment management and telemetry monitoring, the SDK is the ideal place to start creating ENACT applications. The way SDK and APM work together is that the APM code is developed following specific conventions (e.g. naming, interface implementation, etc.) and it's uploaded to the *eu.enact-horizon* Maven Central public namespace [27]. From this location the JARs can be downloaded by the SDK or as described previously, by power end users that prefer to bypass the SDK.

When it comes to conventions that must be taken into account, for now, any component APM jar must provide a main component class that extends the *com.eu.enact.templates.EnactComponentTemplate* abstract class, available to be imported from the ENACT public repository (by adding the dependency snippet displayed in Figure 15). Although there are no requirements for specific implementations, the extended abstract class allows the new component code to be managed by the SDK and programmatically allows it to call any method of the developed code. Actually, upon initialization, the SDK automatically generates services for each referenced APM jar, according to the end user preferences.

```
<dependency>
  <groupId>eu.enact-horizon</groupId>
  <artifactId>enact-template</artifactId>
  <version>0.1</version>
</dependency>
```

Figure 15: Validated and published deployment

The code snippet displayed in Figure 16, showcases how the ZTP component APM jar code is implemented, by extending the *com.eu.enact.templates.EnactComponentTemplate* abstract class.

```
import com.eu.enact.templates.EnactComponentTemplate;

public class ZTPComponent extends EnactComponentTemplate {
    public static class MachineInformation {

        private final static String ZTP_COMPONENT_ENDPOINT = System.getenv("ENACT_APM_ZTP_COMPONENT_ENDPOINT");

        public List<MachineInformation> retrieveAllMachines() throws IOException, InterruptedException {

        public String performAction(String action, String machineId) throws IOException, InterruptedException {

        public MachineInformation retrieveMachine(String machineId) throws IOException, InterruptedException {

    }
}
```

Figure 16: Sample code of component code extending the EnactComponentTemplate

In summary, APM and SDK offer two distinct but complementary pathways for integrating and interacting with CCC components, each tailored to different user needs and levels of expertise. For advanced users and developers who require full control over the configuration and integration of individual components, the direct use of APM JARs provides a powerful and flexible approach. By adding the appropriate Maven dependencies and following the documented guidelines for each APM module, users can access the full functionality of the platform and tailor their applications to specific requirements.

The SDK serves as the primary entry point for users who may be less familiar with the technical intricacies of individual components or who prefer a more guided and automated development process. The synergy between the SDK and APM is enabled through well-defined conventions in code structure and interface implementation, ensuring seamless integration and management of component services.

5. Software Development Kit (SDK)

The Software Development Kit (SDK) significantly simplifies interactions with the ENACT platform, providing streamlined development and integration experiences through library and graphical user interface variants. It ensures standardized, efficient development workflows for developers with varying expertise levels.

5.1 Design Approach

This subsection details the strategic and functional rationale behind the SDK's two-version structure, emphasizing the balance between ease-of-use through a graphical interface and flexibility via direct code integration.

SDK is designed to equip ENACT platform users with a comprehensive set of tools that streamline both development and deployment processes. The Enact platform comprises various components, each with distinct characteristics and functions. SDK standardizes access to these components by delivering only the essential information needed for their operation. It also ensures that interactions with these components are correctly executed, thereby mitigating the risks associated with unauthorized or improper usage that could potentially disrupt the platform.

An additional key function of the SDK is to serve as an interface between the developer and the platform. Acknowledging the variability in developers' expertise, the SDK is available in two variants to accommodate different skill levels. The first option is offered as a Maven library, which can be directly imported into a project. This option requires a solid understanding of Java programming, package management, and API integration, making it more suitable for experienced developers. The second variant is provided as an Eclipse IDE [7] plugin that integrates within the Eclipse workspace. This variant offers a graphical interface through which users can select the required services or components, with the SDK automatically generating the necessary Java code and imports, thereby simplifying integration for less experienced developers.

5.2 General structure and workflow

The Software Development Kit (SDK) is a central element of the ENACT ecosystem, serving as the main interface through which users interact with the platform and deploy applications within the ENACT cluster. As illustrated in Figure 1, the platform architecture comprises multiple interconnected components, each with specific operational logic, data handling procedures, and communication protocols. These components, implemented using a variety of technologies and architectural models, collectively provide the full functionality of the system. Due to this structural heterogeneity, direct interaction with individual components would require users to have an in-depth understanding of the internal behavior and dependencies of the entire platform, thereby complicating the development and deployment process. The SDK abstracts this complexity, enabling streamlined access to the platform's capabilities.

To address this, the SDK—working in conjunction with the Application Programming Model (APM)—provides a unified and consistent interface that abstracts the complexity of the underlying components (Figure 17). It enables users to integrate ENACT functionalities into their applications with reduced effort, facilitating both the development and deployment processes. Furthermore, by mediating access through a controlled software layer, the SDK mitigates the risks associated with

unintended or unauthorized interactions with platform components. This controlled access mechanism helps preserve the stability and integrity of the platform.

Figure 17: SDK - APM Interaction

The development of the SDK has undergone several iterations, each aimed at enhancing functionality, usability, and integration capabilities. The initial version of the SDK was implemented as a basic Eclipse plugin (Figure 18). This early version provided a graphical interface that exposed APM functions but lacked additional logic or utility (Figure 19 and Figure 20). Its role was limited to that of a visual wrapper, offering little added value beyond what was already available through direct interaction with the APM. As such, it was primarily useful for novice developers unfamiliar with direct integration, and its utility was questioned, since more experienced users could bypass it altogether by directly invoking APM functionality.

Figure 18: Initial SDK Dashboard

This limitation led to a significant redesign of the SDK, resulting in its current two-part architecture: a Java library version and a plugin version for the Eclipse IDE (Figure 21). The library version, distributed via a build management system such as Maven, extends beyond the simple exposure of APM methods. It introduces additional helper functions and abstractions that streamline interaction with the platform, and it establishes a standard integration model that other components within ENACT can follow. This ensures consistency and reduces the integration burden across different services.

Figure 19: Incubator Dashboard

Figure 20: Raspberry Pi Controller

Figure 21: Revised SDK Architectural Diagram

The plugin version, although still based on the concept of providing a graphical interface, was restructured to depend on and incorporate the functionality of the library version. This approach ensures that any updates or improvements made to the library are automatically reflected in the plugin, maintaining consistency between the two. The second version of the plugin also featured a more refined user interface and better interaction patterns (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Revised SDK Dashboard

A third and final major revision focused exclusively on improving the plugin version (Figure 23). While the library version had proven stable and was easily integrated into external projects, the plugin suffered from performance and usability issues. Earlier versions of the plugin required users to restart or reload the interface frequently after performing actions, leading to a cumbersome experience and slower development cycles. In response, the latest version of the plugin was redesigned to operate as an integrated part of the Eclipse IDE environment. It now runs persistently in the background, allowing users to access its features without interrupting their workflow. This integration enables users to generate or import code directly into their current development context with minimal overhead.

Figure 23: New SDK Plugin Architectural Diagram

This dual-variant design addresses a wide range of development needs. The library version caters to experienced developers who prefer direct integration and programmatic control. The plugin version, on the other hand, offers more guided experience for users with limited exposure to ENACT’s internal mechanisms. It provides contextual information and automated code generation features that reduce the need for manual configuration and component integration. By supporting both usage scenarios, the SDK ensures accessibility and efficiency across different levels of technical expertise.

5.2.1 Template library overview

The template library plays a foundational role in ensuring consistency and interoperability among all components developed for integration into the ENACT platform. All components are integrated through the Application Programming Model (APM) and subsequently imported into the SDK. The template library defines a standardized structure that these components must adhere to, enabling the SDK—particularly the plugin version—to automatically discover and interact with them in a uniform way. This structure is essential for SDK’s internal automation and processing mechanisms to function correctly across all integrated components, eliminating the need for custom integration logic for each new addition.

The motivation behind this approach lies in the need for scalability and maintainability. As the number of components and extensions to the platform grows, enforcing a consistent interface ensures that new functionality can be introduced without requiring frequent and error-prone refactoring of the SDK or its associated tooling. Components that adhere to the template library can be automatically processed by the SDK’s introspection mechanisms, allowing for features such as dynamic UI updates, automated code generation, and service discovery to function reliably and consistently across all modules.

To facilitate adoption and ease of use, the template library is distributed as a Maven [34] dependency, which can be readily imported by ENACT partners into their own projects. It contains a set of abstract

classes that define mandatory methods and behaviors, which must be implemented or inherited by any component intended for SDK integration. This approach reduces boilerplate, enforces architectural constraints, and standardizes component metadata and behavior across the ecosystem.

A key class within the template library is `EnactComponentTemplate` (Figure 24), which encapsulates essential reflection-based mechanisms required by the SDK for runtime interaction. The abstract class includes methods that allow for dynamic invocation, metadata access, and introspection of available functionalities.

Figure 24: EnactComponentTemplate Class Diagram

This class illustrates several core responsibilities of template components:

- Providing metadata such as component names.
- Allowing for reflective invocation of methods at runtime.
- Enumerating available methods and their parameter types.

These mechanisms are essential for the SDK plugin to render service interfaces dynamically in the UI, validate method signatures, and generate integration stubs without hardcoded logic.

Looking forward, the template library may be extended to include additional base classes or utility interfaces. However, such additions will be designed to maintain backward compatibility and will not introduce breaking changes. The goal of any future updates is to enhance code clarity and structural organization, not to redefine existing behaviors. All critical functionality necessary for the platform's operation has already been established within the current library, and any further enhancements will focus on improving developer experience rather than altering runtime behavior.

5.2.2 Library SDK version

The library version of the ENACT SDK is designed for developers who prefer direct integration and are comfortable working with Java and Maven-based dependency management. It offers a programmatic interface to the ENACT platform, bypassing the Eclipse plugin in favor of direct access to the underlying services. This approach provides greater flexibility and control, particularly for users building automated systems, backend services, or integrating ENACT into non-IDE-based development environments.

The SDK library is distributed as a set of JAR files, each corresponding to a specific component of the ENACT platform. These JARs encapsulate the necessary functionality, interfaces, and bindings required to interact with their respective components. Internally, the library communicates with the Application Programming Model (APM), invoking its services and managing the translation between user-facing methods and low-level operations.

While the APM can be accessed directly, doing so typically requires working with verbose APIs and supplying numerous parameters, many of which can be inferred or derived from context. The SDK library simplifies this interaction by wrapping APM calls in higher-level utility methods. These abstractions reduce boilerplate and improve developer productivity. For example, a method that would ordinarily require ten parameters via the APM might be exposed through the SDK as a two-parameter call, with the remaining values automatically inferred by the SDK based on project context, templates, or internal defaults.

In addition to simplifying APM usage, the SDK library introduces supplementary methods that are not available through the APM alone. These enhancements allow for more precise manipulation of ENACT components and services, giving developers access to functionality tailored to frequent use cases or platform-specific workflows.

The process of using the SDK library begins with importing the relevant JAR files into a project. These include:

- A core SDK JAR, which contains shared logic, abstractions, and base utilities.
- Component-specific JARs, which provide access to individual ENACT modules.
- The template library JAR, which defines the base structure and required methods for any services built or extended using the SDK.

Once the dependencies are included, developers can instantiate and use service classes corresponding to each ENACT component. These service classes are built upon the template definitions and expose a consistent, well-structured API. Developers are free to call these services directly within their own code, integrate them into larger systems, or extend them to suit custom application needs.

By relying on the SDK library rather than the Eclipse plugin, users maintain full control over how SDK functionality is invoked and integrated. This approach is particularly advantageous for experienced developers who prioritize flexibility and prefer to avoid the constraints of IDE-specific tooling.

5.2.3 Eclipse plugin SDK version

The Eclipse Plugin version of the ENACT SDK is designed to provide a user-friendly and accessible interface for integrating ENACT components into Java-based projects. Tailored especially for users who prefer a graphical interface—or those with limited familiarity with direct API-level integration—this version enables a more guided experience within the Eclipse IDE environment.

Once installed, the plugin embeds itself directly into the Eclipse user interface, presenting a dedicated SDK View that remains persistently accessible during the development session (see Figure 25). This integrated view allows users to navigate between functionalities without interrupting their workflow.

Figure 25: IDE Embedded SDK View

Core Functionalities

The SDK plugin is structured around three primary tools accessible via tabbed navigation at the top of the view:

1. Class Importer

This feature (Figure 26) allows the user to import a pre-existing configuration file in YAML [37] format. The YAML file defines one or more ENACT services the user wishes to include in their project. Upon selecting the file, the SDK processes it, validates its structure, and automatically generates the corresponding Java code. This facilitates standardized sharing of configurations across teams or projects.

Figure 26: Class Importer View

2. Class Generator

This view enables users to interactively configure which services they wish to include in their project. The plugin presents a list of available ENACT components (e.g., IncubatorMocked) as selectable entries (Figure 27 and Figure 28). Once selections are made, the user may either:

- Save the configuration as a YAML file for future reuse or sharing.
- Generate Java code directly into their project using the selected services.

Figure 27: Class Generator View

Figure 28: Class Generator Options

3. Function Importer

This tool offers finer control by allowing the user to import individual methods rather than entire services. Upon selecting a service, the plugin displays a list of all available functions, including their names, return types, and parameters (Figure 29). The user may then choose specific functions and insert the corresponding method and stubs directly into their working script. This is particularly useful when full-service integration is unnecessary, and only select functionality is required.

Note: The Function Importer does not modify the YAML configuration or affect code generation. It simply inserts code into the currently active file.

Figure 29: Function Importer View

5.2.3.1 Yaml Configuration Format

The YAML file serves as a portable configuration descriptor for ENACT service integration. It defines which components are to be included, as well as additional metadata required for code generation. The SDK plugin handles YAML creation and parsing internally, so users are not required to write or modify these files manually. Saving configurations in this format allows teams to standardize and reuse service setups efficiently across different environments.

5.2.3.2 Code Auto-Generation

Based on the selected services (either from a loaded YAML or manual selection), the SDK plugin generates the necessary Java classes, service initializations, and method bindings. This automation:

- Reduces boilerplate code.
- Ensures proper usage of ENACT service templates.

Maintains consistency with the underlying SDK library. This plugin-based approach empowers developers to work efficiently within a familiar IDE, while abstracting the complexity of service discovery, configuration formatting, and boilerplate implementation. It is especially effective for rapid prototyping, educational use, or situations where teams need to maintain consistency across multiple contributors.

5.3 Deployment

5.3.1 Template library deployment via Maven Central

The template library is published on Maven Central under ENACT's official repository. For this purpose, a Maven repository was registered using ENACT's designated organization credentials. The library was configured using the pom.xml file and digitally signed with GnuPG [38] to verify the authenticity of the publishing source. After identity verification was completed, the compiled artifacts for the template project were uploaded to Maven Central. This allows users to include the library in their projects directly through standard Maven dependency management.

Library SDK version deployment

The Eclipse plugin SDK version is also deployed to Maven Central under the ENACT organization. The deployment process follows the same procedure as the template library. A Maven repository was set up using ENACT's official credentials, and the SDK project was configured using a pom.xml file.

To ensure authenticity, the artifacts were signed using GnuPG. After successful verification of the developer identity, the SDK JAR files were uploaded to Maven Central. This makes the SDK readily accessible via standard Maven coordinates, allowing developers to integrate it into their Eclipse plugin projects without manual setup.

Eclipse plugin SDK version deployment

The Eclipse plugin SDK version will be deployed as a standalone Eclipse plugin, intended strictly for use within the Eclipse environment. Unlike the template and library components deployed to Maven Central, this version will follow the OSGi (Open Services Gateway initiative [39]) model, which is standard for Eclipse plugin development.

The plugin will be packaged as an OSGi-compliant bundle and deployed through an Eclipse update site or a local plugin repository, depending on the distribution method chosen. This approach ensures compatibility with Eclipse's plugin system and allows for seamless installation via the Eclipse Marketplace or by referencing the update site URL.

The SDK plugin will not be available as a generic Maven artifact, as its usage is specific to Eclipse-based tooling. All required dependencies will be included or referenced via the plugin manifest to support integration within the Eclipse IDE.

6. Applied scenarios for the APM and SDK

6.1 Use case #1: Distributed media and entertainment content management

The first use case demonstrates the practical use of the Enact SDK in accelerating the development of applications that interact with both data processing services and cloud-based storage systems. The goal of this scenario is to show how developers can quickly build applications that extract and handle metadata from video files without needing in-depth knowledge of low-level integration with storage platforms or data validation mechanisms.

The scenario consists of two distinct workflows. In the first workflow (Figure 30), the developer creates a Java application that processes a video file and generates metadata in the form of histograms. This functionality is exposed through a service provided by the SDK, which operates independently of the Application Programming Model (APM). The SDK includes a dedicated video processing component capable of extracting visual data, which the user can invoke directly from their code. Once the metadata is extracted, the application must upload it to MinIO [40], a cloud-based object storage system. To facilitate this, the SDK wraps an APM-provided JAR that manages the upload process. As a result, the user can easily write a script that processes the video and uploads the resulting data without needing to manage the details of connecting to MinIO or manually handling file transfers.

Figure 30: Video processing scenario workflow 1

The second workflow (Figure 31) focuses on retrieving data from MinIO while enforcing access control. In this case, the user develops a second Java application to download the previously uploaded metadata. The SDK assists the user by generating the necessary code to perform the download operation, while the access and retrieval process is governed entirely by the APM through two dedicated JAR files. The first JAR handles communication with Sovity [41], a data sovereignty service that verifies whether the user is authorized to access the requested data. If authorized, Sovity returns a JSON file containing the address of the metadata in MinIO. The second JAR, using the contents of the JSON file, performs the actual download and stores the data locally. The SDK orchestrates this process by exposing both JARs as services that can be easily configured and integrated into the user's application, thereby enabling secure and efficient access to cloud-stored metadata. This scenario highlights the SDK's capacity to abstract and automate common tasks in application development, allowing users to focus on functionality without being burdened by the complexities of integration and security validation.

Figure 31: Video processing scenario workflow 2

The other two scenarios which will be presented next will have a similar approach with slightly different implementations according to the specific use-cases.

6.2 Use Case #2: Transforming rowing Regattas La Concha Flag Tracking with VR Technologies

The technical focus of this pilot is to enable a next-generation immersive experience for the Regata de la Concha event [42] by integrating real-time data streams, user interaction, and adaptive orchestration within the ENACT ecosystem.

The data flow in Use Case 2 (Regata de la Concha) is structured around the real-time capture, processing and delivery of multimodal content, including GPS signals, audio-visual streams and user interaction data. EITB [43] provides the primary input sources, including live video of the regatta and geolocation data from each boat. This information is transmitted to the core integration environment managed by Osoigo [44], where it is combined with frontend interaction data such as camera selection, survey responses, and session activity.

EITB acts as the primary data source, delivering both video and geolocation inputs. These are transmitted to the core integration environment managed by Osoigo, which serves as the central aggregation and delivery node. Osoigo combines backend data with frontend interaction metrics and

exposes the final user-facing experience through EITB's website. Upon accessing the interface, users are redirected to Osoigo's immersive frontend, where they can:

- Interact with multiple synchronized camera feeds.
- Participate in quizzes or polls.
- Explore a 3D visualisation of the regatta environment.

Osoigo acts as the central node for aggregation and delivery, ensuring that both live and processed data streams are accessible through a web-based immersive interface. Users access the experience via EITB's website, which redirects to Osoigo's frontend where they can interact with multiple camera feeds, participate in polls, and navigate an immersive 3D view of the regatta environment. All user experience data (QoE [45]) and service metrics (QoS [46]) are monitored or inferred by ENACT components, including the Telemetry module, AI Layer and Orchestrator, to enable dynamic adaptation of the content flow.

The system relies on a distributed infrastructure composed of cloud-level (A) and edge-level (B) nodes. Video and data flows originate in the cloud and are selectively delivered to edge nodes closer to users, with ENACT managing adaptive routing and content switching based on performance indicators and interaction behaviour. This structure supports low-latency delivery and real-time response to contextual changes during the event, forming the basis for ENACT's cognitive orchestration capabilities within the pilot.

6.3 Use Case #3: Hyper-Distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin Initiative

The Fujitsu pilot demonstrates how the ENACT platform can be used to implement scalable, resilient digital twin ecosystems, particularly focused on managing and visualizing urban mobility and environmental data. This use case leverages ENACT's orchestration, data ingestion, and plugin frameworks to support a Digital Twin Utilizer (DTU) – a system that aggregates, processes, and analyzes multimodal sensor and simulation data streams in near real time.

The DTU aggregates information from several sources:

- Vehicle fleet simulation (main data source).
- Air quality data from Poland.
- Weather data from Polish regions.
- GPS locations of public transport in Polish cities.

These streams are managed through a set of dedicated Kafka [47] topics, where preprocessing scripts publish and update sensor data in real time. The system uses Apache Flink [48] for data stream processing and Kubernetes for orchestrating and scaling the deployed services. The ENACT SDK and APM play a central role in configuring the Digital Twin Utilizer (DTU) plugins, managing data flow through Kafka, and connecting visualization tools such as Integra, a user interface for monitoring and control.

Specifically, the Application Programming Model (APM) provides secure, programmatic access to backend services, including Kafka brokers, MinIO object storage, and Flink operators. The SDK simplifies plugin development and deployment by auto-generating Kafka handler templates and assisting in binding sensor data streams to their processing workflows. Plugins are developed as Java

classes extending the ENACT StateHandler interface, with examples like speed-monitoring plugins that process vehicle telemetry and emit alerts when thresholds are exceeded.

The data processing pipeline begins with preprocessing scripts that ingest raw data and populate Kafka source topics with structured objects (such as air quality, weather, and transport data). The ENACT-managed plugins then consume this data in near real time, applying rule-based transformations, threshold detection, or alert triggering as needed. The processed data is subsequently visualized through Integra or persisted to storage backends such as MinIO [40] or PostgreSQL [49]. Overall system orchestration and dynamic scaling are handled via Kubernetes and Flink, with monitoring and recovery mechanisms powered by the ENACT orchestrator stack.

7. Conclusions

This deliverable has outlined the design, implementation, and integration processes for the ENACT Application Programming Model (APM) and the Software Development Kit (SDK), highlighting their respective roles in enabling secure, modular, and scalable development of hyper-distributed applications within the ENACT ecosystem.

The document began with an analysis of the technical requirements that shaped the design of the APM and SDK, emphasizing principles such as exclusive access to ENACT Cognitive Compute Continuum (CCC), secure communication, user role management, and flexible service integration. The APM was presented as a lightweight but powerful set of Java libraries, externally deployed via Maven Central, allowing developers to interact programmatically with internal ENACT services without direct endpoint exposure. The evolution from a functional entity within the CCC to an external, downloadable resource marked a significant architectural paradigm shift, aligning the APM with industry-standard development workflows.

Complementing the APM, the SDK was designed to simplify the development process through two delivery variants: a Maven-based library version and an Eclipse plugin version. The SDK provides dynamic code generation, component discovery, and user-friendly integration mechanisms, abstracting the complexity of service orchestration and policy management. Together, the APM and SDK create a layered architecture where developers can choose the appropriate level of control and abstraction depending on their technical expertise and project needs.

Applied scenarios—including the MOG, Osoigo, and Fujitsu pilots—demonstrated the practical utility of these tools across diverse domains, such as real-time video processing, immersive media orchestration, and urban mobility analytics. These pilots validated the extensibility and modularity of the APM-SDK integration, as well as their effectiveness in managing distributed service orchestration, telemetry monitoring, and access control in edge-to-cloud environments.

The deliverable concludes by reaffirming the key goals of the ENACT initiative: to provide secure, interoperable, and developer-friendly tools that empower stakeholders to build, deploy, and manage hyper-distributed applications. The APM and SDK will continue to evolve in alignment with platform needs, with future extensions planned for Python-based environments and enhanced integration support for AI-driven orchestration and compliance monitoring.

8. References

- [1] <https://enact-horizon.eu/>
- [2] <https://central.sonatype.com/>
- [3] <https://www.mog-technologies.com/>
- [4] <https://www.osoigo.com/>
- [5] <https://www.fujitsu.com/pl/about/local/warsaw/>
- [6] <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/application-programming-model>
- [7] <https://www.eclipse.org/>
- [8] <https://marketplace.eclipse.org/>
- [9] <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/software-development-kit>
- [10] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HTTPS>
- [11] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Transport_Layer_Security
- [12] <https://www.imperva.com/learn/application-security/man-in-the-middle-attack-mitm/>
- [13] <https://www.cloudflare.com/learning/ddos/glossary/denial-of-service/>
- [14] <https://www.progress.com/blogs/use-aes-256-encryption-secure-data>
- [15] <https://aws.amazon.com/kms/>
- [16] <https://www.doppler.com/guides/aws-guides/aws-vault>
- [17] <https://oauth.net/2/>
- [18] <https://jwt.io/introduction>
- [19] <https://www.cloudflare.com/learning/access-management/what-is-mutual-tls/>
- [20] <https://www.cloudflare.com/learning/cdn/glossary/reverse-proxy/>
- [21] <https://spring.io/projects/spring-boot>
- [22] <https://www.docker.com/>
- [23] <https://kubernetes.io/>
- [24] <https://k3s.io/>
- [25] <https://nextcloud.enact-horizon.eu/index.php/f/157431>
- [26] <https://keyserver.ubuntu.com>
- [27] <https://central.sonatype.com/namespaces/eu.enact-horizon>
- [28] <https://nextcloud.enact-horizon.eu/index.php/f/630052>
- [29] <https://www.siemens.com/at/de.html>
- [30] <https://www.cloudflare.com/>
- [31] <https://github.com/cloudflare/cloudflared>
- [32] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Secure_Shell
- [33] <https://www.ssh.com/academy/ssh/tunneling-example>
- [34] <https://maven.apache.org/>
- [35] <https://my.sonatype.com/>
- [36] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pretty_Good_Privacy
- [37] <https://yaml.org/>
- [38] <https://www.gnupg.org/>
- [39] <https://www.osgi.org/resources/what-is-osgi/>
- [40] <https://min.io/>
- [41] <https://sovity.de/en/sovity-en/>
- [42] <https://sansebastiandetails.com/calendar/regatta>
- [43] <https://www.eitb.eus/en/>
- [44] <https://www.osoigo.com/>
- [45] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quality_of_experience

- [46] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quality_of_service
- [47] <https://kafka.apache.org/>
- [48] <https://flink.apache.org/>
- [49] <https://www.postgresql.org/>